

1 **Supplementary Information**

2 *In situ* calibration of a tube passive sampler in wastewater
3 effluent with adjustable volumetric flow for assessment of
4 micro-pollutants with fluctuating concentrations

5 Tobias Hensel^a, Jörg-Helge Hein^b, Thorsten Reemtsma^c, Alexander Sperlich^a,

6 Regina Gnirß^a, Frederik Zietzschmann^{a*}

7 ^aBerliner Wasserbetriebe, Neue Jüdenstraße 1, 10179 Berlin, Germany

8 ^bGCI GmbH, Bahnhofstraße 19, 15711 Königs Wusterhausen, Germany

9 ^cHelmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ), Department of Analytical
10 Chemistry, Permoserstrasse 15, 04318 Leipzig, Germany

11 *frederik.zietzschmann@bwb.de

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32 Fig. S1: Biofouling and suspended matter depositions on discs and disc retainer of the
33 large passive sampler over Time.

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35 Fig. S2: Experiment setup at wastewater treatment plant near Berlin. On the left the
36 two large tube passive sampler devices with attached controllers. On the right the
37 automatic sampler for reference sampling.

Restek Resprep Resin SPE

Biotage Atlantic C18

Biotage Atlantic HLB

Biotage Atlantic DVB

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39 Fig. S3: Uptake behavior of different disc materials from wastewater in laboratory
40 experiments. The dodecagon represents 100 % recovery on the discs in reference to
41 the amount of the respective compound in the wastewater sample. The more the
42 hatched area approaches the circle line the better the material; values inside the
43 dodecagon mean <100% recovery, values outside >100% recovery.

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45 Fig. S4: Comparison of normalized uptake of DVB and HLB discs after 48 hours over
 46 volume flow for each individual OMP.

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48 Fig. S5: Calibration models for different compounds via *in situ* calibration of the mini
 49 tube passive sampler in WWTP effluent. The y-axis on each graph corresponds to the
 50 sampled amount of analyte on the disc. The top rows show the classical calibration
 51 via the exposure time (x-axis), the lower rows show the feed water load dependent
 52 calibration of the tube passive sampler (x-axis), respectively. Values shown are means
 53 of two replicates.

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55 Fig. S6: A: Flow simulation of the mini Tube Passive Sampling after optimization. B:
 56 Dimensions of the mini TPS including the disc retainer.

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58 Fig. S7: Order of the individual experiments. The widths of the bars representing the
 59 individual durations of the consecutive experiments relative to each other.

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Fig. S8: Calibration models for different compounds via *in situ* calibration of the maxi tube passive sampler in WWTP effluent. The y-axis on each graph corresponds to the sampled amount of analyte on the disc. The top rows show the classical calibration via the exposure time (x-axis), the lower rows show the feed water load dependent calibration of the tube passive sampler (x-axis), respectively. Values shown are means of four replicates.

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68 Fig. S9: Model plot of valsartan acid via *in situ* calibration of the maxi tube passive
 69 sampler in WWTP effluent. The y-axis on each graph corresponds to the sampled
 70 amount of analyte on the disc. The top row shows the classical calibration via the
 71 exposure time (x-axis), the lower row shows the feed water load dependent calibration
 72 of the tube passive sampler (x-axis), respectively. Values shown are means of four
 73 replicates.

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75 Fig. S10: Comparison of amount vs. Time (A and B), amount/ $c_{w,TWA}$ vs. Time (C and
 76 D) and amount vs. feed water load (E and D) for Metoprolol and Tolytriazole from large
 77 TPS. Arrows follow same values through the plots. For C and D: values in brackets
 78 result from disc-loads above the individual threshold ($2/3$ of the maximum disc-load).
 79 Values shown are means of four replicates.

80

81 Fig. S11: Comparison of amount vs. Time (A and B), amount/ $c_{w,TWA}$ vs. Time (C and
 82 D) and amount vs. feed water load (E and D) for Metoprolol and Tolyltriazole from
 83 miniaturized TPS. Arrows follow same values through the plots. For C and D: values
 84 in brackets result from disc-loads above the individual threshold ($2/3$ of the maximum
 85 disc-load). The datapoints result from means of duplicates.

86 Tables

87 Tab S1: Standards and isotope-labelled standards.

#	Compound	Abbreviation	CAS	Purity in %	Exact Mass in m/z	Internal Standard (IS) acronym	LOQ ¹ (µg/L)
1	1H-Benzotriazole		95-14-7	99	120.0556	Benzo[1,2,3-c]triazole d4	0.05
2	Tolyltriazole		136-85-6	99.8	134.0713	Benzo[1,2,3-c]triazole d4	0.1
3	2-(Methylthio)benzothiazole	MTBT	615-22-5	97.1	182.0093	Benzo[1,2,3-c]triazole d4	0.2
4	Tributylphosphate	TBP	126-73-8	99	267.1720	TBP d27	0.2
5	Tris-(2-chlorethyl)-phosphate	TCEP	115-96-8	97.6	284.9612	TBP d27	0.2
6	Tris-(2-chlorisopropyl)-phosphate	T CPP	13674-84-5	99.7	327.0081	TBP d27	0.4
7	Diethyltoluamide	DEET	134-62-3	98	192.1383	DEET d7	0.1
8	4-Acetamidoantipyrine	AAA	83-15-8	99.5	246.1237	Phenazone d3	0.07
9	1-Acetyl-2-phenylhydrazine	AMPH	114-83-0	99.9	165.1022	Phenazone d3	0.1
10	4-Dimethylaminoantipyrine	DMAA	58-15-1	99.5	232.1444	Dihydrocarbamazepine	0.09
11	Dimethylpyrazolon	DP	3201-28-3	95	113.0709	-	0.09
12	4-Formylaminoantipyrine	FAA	1672-58-8	95	232.1081	Phenazone d3	0.07
13	Phenazone		60-80-0	99.3	189.1022	Phenazone d3	0.08
14	Propyphenazone		479-92-5	99.3	231.1492	Phenazone d3	0.09
15	Diclofenac		15307-86-5	99.7	296.0240	Diclofenac d4	0.1
16	Metoprolol		51384-51-1	99.9	268.1907	Propranolol d6	0.06
17	Valsartan		137862-53-4	99.4	436.2343	Propranolol d6	n.d.
18	Valsartan acid		164265-78-5	97.1	267.0877	Propranolol d6	n.d.
19	Acesulfame		33665-90-6	100	164.0012	Propranolol d6	n.d.
20	lomeprol		78649-41-9	96	777.8613	Propranolol d6	n.d.

88 ¹ According to DIN 32645:2008-11
89 n.d.: not determined

90 Sections

91 Section S1: Materials and Chemicals

92 The analytical standards were purchased as single substances by Neochema GmbH
93 (Bodenheim, GER). For more Info see Tab. S1. The corresponding quality control
94 standards were purchased as single substances from LGC Lt. (Teddington, UK). In
95 addition to these, available deuterated calibration standards were purchased also from
96 LGC Lt. (Teddington, UK) and were used for calibration. As sorption discs, we applied
97 solid-phase extraction (SPE) discs Atlantic® DVB (Divinylbenzene, 47 mm), Atlantic®
98 HLB-H (Hydrophilic-Lipophilic-Balanced, 47 mm) and Atlantic® C-18, purchased from
99 Biotage Sweden AB (Uppsala, SWE) as well as Resprep-C18 purchased from Restek
100 (Bellefonte, USA). LC-MS-grade Methanol for sample and disc preparation as well as
101 LC measurements was purchased from Honeywell (Morristown, USA). Other
102 chemicals were purchased from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, GER). Ultra-pure water with

103 a resistivity of >0.05 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and <3 ppm TOC resulted from an BerryPURE® ultra-pure
104 water system (Berrytech, Harthausen Germany). For concentration of the eluates, a
105 TurboVap II® water bath from Zymark Corp. (Hopkinton, USA) with corresponding
106 vials was used.

107 Section S2: Quality Assurance and Quality Control

108 Laboratory blanks of the passive sampling discs showed no contamination or blank
109 values resulting from disc handling or from the discs their selves. During LC-HRMS
110 analysis, control standards were measured every 30-40 samples to keep track of any
111 changes of intensity.

112 Section S3: Determination of the absolute residual error

113 The weaknesses of interpreting a linear regression with no-intercept via the coefficient
114 of determination R^2 is discussed in the literature¹⁻³. Briefly, most computing software
115 will use an erroneous way to calculate R^2 near the forced intercept at the origin. For
116 reason of comparison to other regression models we use the absolute residual error
117 (ARE).

$$ARE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_n - \hat{y}_n)^2}{df}} \quad (1)$$

118 With y_n being the measured value, \hat{y}_n the value determined by the linear regression for
119 n values and df the degrees of freedom.

120 References

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